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Impulsivity, perceived self-regulatory success in dieting, and body mass in children and adolescents: A moderated mediation model

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Abstract

22 Impulsivity has been suggested to contribute to overeating and obesity. However, findings are
23 inconsistent and it appears that only specific facets of impulsivity are related to eating-related
24 variables and to body mass. In the current study, relationships between self-reported
25 impulsivity, perceived self-regulatory success in dieting, and objectively measured body mass
26 were examined in $N = 122$ children and adolescents. Scores on attentional and motor
27 impulsivity interactively predicted perceived self-regulatory success in dieting, but not body
28 mass: Higher attentional impulsivity was associated with lower perceived self-regulatory
29 success at high levels of motor impulsivity, but not at low levels of motor impulsivity. A
30 moderated mediation model revealed an indirect effect of attentional and motor impulsivity
31 on body mass, which was mediated by perceived self-regulatory success in dieting. Thus,
32 results show that only specific facets of impulsivity are relevant in eating- and weight-
33 regulation and interact with each other in the prediction of these variables. These facets of
34 impulsivity, however, are not directly related to higher body mass, but indirectly via lower
35 success in eating-related self-regulation in children and adolescents.

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Keywords

42 Impulsivity; Barratt Impulsiveness Scale; Perceived Self-Regulatory Success in Dieting; Body
43 mass index; Obesity; Children; Adolescents

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Introduction

45 Impulsivity refers to a predisposition toward rapid, unplanned reactions to internal or
46 external stimuli without regard to the negative consequences of these reactions (Moeller,
47 Barratt, Dougherty, Schmitz, & Swann, 2001). High impulsivity levels have been suggested to
48 contribute to overeating (e.g., binge eating in individuals with eating disorders) and obesity
49 (Guerrieri, Nederkoorn, & Jansen, 2008; Lavender & Mitchell, 2015). For example, it has
50 been found that overweight or obese individuals react more impulsively than normal-weight
51 participants do in behavioral tasks (e.g., go/no-go, stop signal, or delay discounting tasks) in
52 samples of adults (Mobbs, Iglesias, Golay, & Van der Linden, 2011; Nederkoorn, Smulders,
53 Havermans, Roefs, & Jansen, 2006; Weller, Cook, Avsar, & Cox, 2008) and children (Fields,
54 Sabet, & Reynolds, 2013; Nederkoorn, Braet, Van Eijs, Tanghe, & Jansen, 2006; Wirt,
55 Hundsdörfer, Schreiber, Kesztyüs, & Steinacker, 2014). Similarly, it has been found that
56 overweight or obese individuals report higher impulsivity than normal-weight participants do
57 using questionnaire measures in samples of adults (Mobbs, Crépin, Thiéry, Golay, & Van der
58 Linden, 2010; Rydén et al., 2003) and children (Nederkoorn, Braet, et al., 2006). Furthermore,
59 higher impulsivity (lower motor response inhibition in particular) prospectively predicted
60 weight gain or lower dieting success in children (Nederkoorn, Jansen, Mulkens, & Jansen,
61 2007; Reinert, Po'e, & Barkin, 2013).

62 Findings are, however, inconsistent. For example, scores on impulsivity measures
63 were unrelated to body mass in several studies in adults (Hendrick, Luo, Zhang, & Li, 2012;
64 Koritzky, Yechiam, Bukay, & Milman, 2012; Loeber et al., 2012) and in children (Fields et
65 al., 2013; Verdejo-García et al., 2010). In other studies, impulsivity was associated with body
66 mass or weight gain, but only as a function of moderating variables such as responsiveness to
67 food cues in adults (Houben, Nederkoorn, & Jansen, 2014; Meule & Platte, 2016;

68 Nederkoorn, Houben, Hofmann, Roefs, & Jansen, 2010) and children (Nederkoorn, Coelho,
69 Guerrieri, Houben, & Jansen, 2012).

70 These inconsistent findings may be, in part, explained by the fact that only specific
71 facets of impulsivity are associated with body mass (Mobbs et al., 2010). For example, one of
72 the most widely used self-report measures for the assessment of impulsivity, the *Barratt*
73 *Impulsiveness Scale* (BIS; Stanford et al., 2009), comprises three subscales representing
74 *attentional impulsivity* (i.e., inability to focus attention or concentrate), *motor impulsivity* (i.e.,
75 acting spontaneously or without thinking), and *non-planning impulsivity* (i.e., lack of future
76 orientation or forethought; Patton, Stanford, & Barratt, 1995). Emerging evidence suggests
77 that particularly attentional and motor impulsivity, but not non-planning impulsivity, are
78 related to measures of overeating and to body mass (Meule, 2013; Meule & Blechert, 2016).

79 In addition to the finding that only specific impulsivity facets are related to eating- and
80 weight-regulation, it has also been found that these impulsivity facets interact with each other
81 when predicting eating behavior and body mass. Higher scores on attentional impulsivity in
82 combination with higher scores on motor impulsivity predicted percent body fat and self-
83 reported binge eating severity in female students (Meule & Platte, 2015). Likewise,
84 attentional and motor impulsivity interactively predicted intake of sweet foods in the
85 laboratory in female students (Kakoschke, Kemps, & Tiggemann, 2015). To conclude, it
86 appears that when both attentional and motor impulsivity levels are high, unhealthy food
87 intake or overeating as well as body mass are elevated in adults.

88 Another consideration when examining associations between impulsivity and obesity
89 is how an impulsive personality translates into higher body mass. Specifically, as impulsivity
90 is a construct that does not cover energy intake or expenditure, it is implausible that it affects
91 fat mass directly. Higher impulsivity can only lead to higher body mass through mediating
92 mechanisms, for example, eating behavior. For instance, Murphy, Stojek, and MacKillop

93 (2014) found that the relationship between trait impulsivity and body mass was mediated by
94 self-reported addiction-like eating. Importantly, this indirect effect was observed in the
95 absence of a direct relationship between impulsivity and body mass. Thus, it is likely that
96 being impulsive may increase the likelihood of falling prey to food temptations, which in turn
97 results in weight gain.

98 In the current study, it was expected that similar findings would be found in a sample
99 of children and adolescents with a wide range in body mass. Specifically, a self-report
100 measure of perceived self-regulatory success in dieting was used, which has been previously
101 found to be associated with both impulsivity and body mass (Meule, Papies, & Kübler, 2012).
102 It was expected that particularly attentional and motor impulsivity would be associated with
103 lower perceived self-regulatory success in dieting and with a higher body mass. Moreover, it
104 was expected that attentional and motor impulsivity would be *interactively* associated with
105 these measures: perceived self-regulatory success in dieting was expected to be lowest and
106 body mass was expected to be highest at high levels of both attentional and motor impulsivity.
107 Finally, it was tested if perceived self-regulatory success in dieting mediated the relationships
108 of attentional and motor impulsivity with body mass and, thus, may represent a psychological
109 proxy variable or mechanism through which behavioral control-related impulsivity facets
110 influence body mass.

111 Methods

112 *Participants*

113 The study was approved by the ethical review board of the University of Salzburg and
114 all participants (and, when appropriate, their parents) signed informed consent. Participants
115 were recruited during routine examinations at the obesity clinic of the Paracelsus Medical
116 University and from public schools in Salzburg (Austria). The study was advertised as a study
117 about the neural processing of food cues (cf. procedure section below). One-hundred and

118 twenty-two children and adolescents (51.60% female, $n = 63$) between 10 and 18 years of age
119 ($M = 13.61$ years, $SD = 2.18$) completed all measures used in the current analyses. Age- and
120 gender-specific mean body mass index (BMI) percentile based on German reference values
121 (Kromeyer-Hauschild et al., 2001) was $M = 74.43$ ($SD = 32.32$) and mean standardized BMI
122 (zBMI) was $M = 1.22$ ($SD = 1.51$). It is recommended to use the third, 10th, 90th, and 97th
123 percentile for defining severe underweight, moderate underweight, overweight, and obesity,
124 respectively (Kromeyer-Hauschild et al., 2001). Using these cut-off values, 1.60% were
125 severely underweight ($n = 2$; $M_{zBMI} = -2.10$, $SD = 0.14$), 4.10% were moderately underweight
126 ($n = 5$; $M_{zBMI} = -1.62$, $SD = 0.24$), 37.70% had normal weight ($n = 46$; $M_{zBMI} = -0.06$, $SD =$
127 0.69), 10.70% were overweight ($n = 13$; $M_{zBMI} = 1.52$, $SD = 0.17$), and 45.90% were obese (n
128 $= 56$; $M_{zBMI} = 2.57$, $SD = 0.52$) in the present sample.

129 *Measures*

130 *Barratt Impulsiveness Scale – short form (BIS-15)*. The German version of the BIS-15
131 (Meule, Vögele, & Kübler, 2011; Spinella, 2007) was used as a self-report measure of trait
132 impulsivity. This 15-item questionnaire includes three subscales, each consisting of five
133 items, representing *attentional impulsivity* (e.g., “I am restless at lectures or talks.”), *motor*
134 *impulsivity* (e.g., “I act on the spur of the moment.”), and *non-planning impulsivity* (e.g., “I
135 plan tasks carefully.” [inverted]). Items are scored on a four-point scale with response
136 categories ranging from *rarely/never* to *almost always/always*. Higher scores represent higher
137 impulsivity. Validity has been demonstrated by positive relationships with other self-report
138 impulsivity measures and with behavioral impulsivity tasks (e.g., Aichert et al., 2012; Lange
139 & Eggert, 2015; Meule & Kübler, 2014; Meule et al., 2011). Internal consistencies were $\alpha =$
140 $.43$ (attentional), $\alpha = .74$ (motor), and $\alpha = .73$ (non-planning) in the current study.

141 *Perceived Self-Regulatory Success in Dieting Scale (PSRS)*. The German version of
142 the PSRS (Fishbach, Friedman, & Kruglanski, 2003; Meule et al., 2012) was used as a self-

143 report measure of self-regulatory success in dieting. This three-item measure asks how
144 successful participants are in watching their weight or losing weight and how easy it is for
145 them to stay in shape. Items are scored on a seven-point scale anchored *not successful/not*
146 *difficult* and *very successful/very difficult*. Higher scores represent higher perceived self-
147 regulatory success in dieting. Validity has been demonstrated by negative relationships with
148 other questionnaire measures that are associated with self-regulatory failure in eating behavior
149 control and with BMI (Meule et al., 2012). Internal consistency was $\alpha = .68$ in the current
150 study.

151 *Body mass.* Height was measured in centimeters with a body height meter and body
152 weight was measured in kilogram with a digital scale in the laboratory. BMI was calculated as
153 weight in kilogram divided by squared height in meters.

154 *Procedure*

155 Participants were tested individually and completed the BIS-15 and the PSRS in the
156 laboratory. They were assisted by the experimenter during questionnaire completion in case of
157 comprehension difficulties. The study also included EEG recording amongst other measures,
158 results of which are described elsewhere (Hofmann, Ardel-Gattinger, Paulmichl, Weghuber,
159 & Blechert, 2015; Meule, Hofmann, Weghuber, Ardel-Gattinger, & Blechert, 2015). At the
160 end of the testing session, body height and weight was measured. Participation was
161 reimbursed with €20.

162 *Data analyses*

163 Linear regression analyses were used to examine moderation and mediation effects
164 with PROCESS for SPSS (Hayes, 2013). Specifically, a moderated mediation model (model
165 no. 12 in PROCESS) was tested, in which scores on all three BIS-15 subscales, their two-way
166 interactions, and the three-way interaction of all BIS-15 subscales were used as predictor

167 variables for both PSRS scores and BMI percentiles (Figure 1A). Predictor variables were
168 mean-centered before calculating the product terms. Significant interactions were followed-up
169 with simple slopes analysis at high (+1SD) and low (-1SD) values of the moderator variable
170 (Hayes, 2013). Exact p -values are reported for significant regression weights ($p < .05$), except
171 when $p < .001$. P -values $\geq .05$ are denoted as *ns*. Furthermore, PSRS scores were used as
172 mediating variable between BIS-15 scores and BMI percentiles (Figure 1A). Indirect (i.e.,
173 mediating) effects were evaluated with 95% bias-corrected confidence intervals based on
174 10,000 bootstrap samples. When the confidence interval does not contain zero, this means that
175 the indirect effect can be considered statistically significant (Hayes, 2013). If the presence of
176 such an indirect effect depends on the value of a moderating variable, this is an indication of
177 moderated mediation. Results were similar when using the standardized BMI instead of BMI
178 percentiles and, thus, only results with BMI percentiles are reported. Also, including sex and
179 age as covariates did not change interpretation of results and, thus, results are presented
180 without covariates.

181 Results

182 Descriptive statistics of and correlations between study variables are depicted in Table
183 1. Perceived self-regulatory success in dieting was negatively correlated with body mass and
184 with attentional and non-planning impulsivity. Attentional and motor impulsivity were
185 positively correlated with each other.

186 Non-planning impulsivity negatively predicted PSRS scores (Table 2). Moreover,
187 there was an interactive effect between attentional and motor impulsivity when predicting
188 PSRS scores (Table 2). Examination of the nature of this interaction revealed that attentional
189 impulsivity negatively predicted PSRS scores, but only at high levels of motor impulsivity
190 and not at low levels of motor impulsivity, that is, PSRS scores were lowest when both
191 attentional and motor impulsivity were high (Figure 2). In turn, PSRS scores negatively

192 predicted BMI percentiles (Table 2). Testing the indirect effect of BIS-15 scores on BMI
193 percentiles via PSRS scores revealed that PSRS scores mediated the association between
194 attentional impulsivity and body mass, but only at high levels of motor impulsivity and not at
195 low or medium levels of motor impulsivity (Table 3).

196 The empirical moderated mediation model is displayed in Figure 2B and can be
197 summarized as follows: Although there was no direct association between attentional
198 impulsivity and body mass, there was an indirect association between attentional impulsivity
199 and body mass via perceived self-regulatory success in dieting. This indirect association,
200 however, was only present at high levels of motor impulsivity. Although non-planning
201 impulsivity was also associated with perceived self-regulatory success in dieting, it did not
202 moderate the effect of attentional impulsivity on body mass.

203 Discussion

204 The current study investigated the relationships of three facets of trait impulsivity with
205 perceived self-regulatory success in dieting and body mass in children and adolescents. It was
206 found that higher attentional impulsivity and, contrary to expectations, non-planning
207 impulsivity correlated with lower perceived self-regulatory success in dieting. There were no
208 correlations between impulsivity subscales and body mass. However, an indirect effect of
209 impulsivity on body mass was found: attentional and motor impulsivity were interactively
210 related to perceived self-regulatory success in dieting, which was, in turn, related to body
211 mass. Specifically, higher attentional impulsivity was associated with lower perceived self-
212 regulatory success in dieting only when motor impulsivity was also high. This lower
213 perceived self-regulatory success in dieting was then associated with higher body mass.

214 These findings partially replicate, but extend previous findings. The negative
215 correlation between attentional impulsivity and PSRS scores is in line with several previous
216 studies in adults (Meule, 2013; Meule et al., 2012; van Koningsbruggen, Stroebe, & Aarts,

217 2013), which indicates that attentional impulsivity appears to be a personality trait associated
218 with reduced eating-related self-regulation. Unexpectedly, non-planning impulsivity was
219 negatively correlated with PSRS scores as well. While it has been suggested that non-
220 planning impulsivity may only play a minor role in eating- and weight-regulation (Meule,
221 2013), it has indeed been found to be negatively correlated with the PSRS in at least one study
222 (van Koningsbruggen et al., 2013). Similarly, non-planning impulsivity was associated with
223 striatal brain activations during high-calorie versus low-calorie food choices (van der Laan,
224 Barendse, Viergever, & Smeets, 2015) and an attentional bias towards high-calorie food cues
225 (Meule & Platte, 2016). Thus, although non-planning impulsivity may not be directly related
226 to body mass and demonstrated inconsistent relationships with eating-related measures, it may
227 indeed be associated with a higher reactivity to high-calorie food cues, which ultimately
228 increases the likelihood of being unsuccessful in regulating high-calorie food intake.

229 The interactive effect between attentional and motor impulsivity when predicting
230 PSRS scores is in line with previous findings in female students, which showed that higher
231 attentional impulsivity in combination with high motor impulsivity predicted higher binge
232 eating frequency (Meule & Platte, 2015) and higher intake of sweet foods in the laboratory
233 (Kakoschke et al., 2015). Contrary to a previous study (Meule & Platte, 2015), however, this
234 interactive effect could not be found when predicting body mass. While this discrepancy may
235 be related to age differences between the two studies, it was found in the current study that
236 there was an indirect effect of the interaction between attentional and motor impulsivity on
237 body mass, which was mediated by perceived self-regulatory success in dieting. This is
238 reasonable as impulsivity has been suggested as a personality trait that potentially increases
239 the risk for engaging in various maladaptive behaviors (e.g., substance use, binge eating,
240 gambling), but is usually manifested in only one or few of these behaviors (Moeller et al.,
241 2001; Shaffer et al., 2004). Hence, high impulsivity (i.e., high attentional and motor
242 impulsivity in particular) does not result in higher body mass directly, but does so only

243 indirectly as it decreases the likelihood that a person can successfully regulate their food
244 intake.

245 On that note, results emphasize the need to go beyond BMI as a dependent variable
246 predicted by psychological variables. Specifically, they suggest that research on psychological
247 determinants (such as impulsivity) needs to include psychological outcome measures (such as
248 perceived self-regulatory success in dieting or eating styles such as addiction-like food
249 consumption, cf. Murphy et al., 2014) in addition to BMI, which is subject to many
250 influencing factors, including non-psychological ones. As PSRS scores were significantly, but
251 only moderately, correlated with BMI, perceived self-regulatory success in dieting –
252 reflecting participants' own experience of their ability to influence their weight – represents a
253 construct, which is related to, yet distinct from body mass and, thus, may be a useful,
254 additional outcome measure in, for example, weight-loss interventions.

255 Interpretation of results is limited by the cross-sectional nature of the study and, thus,
256 the putative causal relationships between study variables (impulsivity → self-regulatory
257 success in dieting → body mass) need to be established with longitudinal designs. However,
258 as self-reported impulsivity is considered a stable trait (e.g., as indicated by high retest-
259 reliability of the BIS; Meule, Mayerhofer, et al., 2015; Stanford et al., 2009) and has been
260 found to prospectively predict weight gain (e.g., Meule & Platte, 2016; Nederkoorn et al.,
261 2010), it is likely that the hypothetical causal directions tested in the current study are valid. A
262 second limitation relates to the use of the BIS-15 and the PSRS in children and adolescents.
263 Although reliability and validity of these measures have been shown in adults (Meule,
264 Mayerhofer, et al., 2015; Meule et al., 2012; Meule et al., 2011; Spinella, 2007), data in
265 children and adolescents are missing. While internal consistency of the PSRS was comparable
266 to values found in adults, internal consistency of the BIS-15's attentional impulsivity subscale
267 was very low in the current study, which suggests that the scale may not be as appropriate in

268 children and adolescents as it is in adults. Nevertheless, as correlates of the attentional
269 impulsivity subscale were similar to those found in adults (Meule, 2013; Meule et al., 2012),
270 it appears that the low internal consistency did not adversely affect the current results. Finally,
271 sample size was relatively small for the quite complex statistical model tested in the current
272 analyses. Given the very small effect sizes of the relationship between BIS-15 scores and BMI
273 in adults (Meule & Blechert, 2016), it may well be that some effects (e.g., the non-interactive
274 effects of attentional and motor impulsivity scores in the regression analyses) would have
275 been significant with a larger sample size.

276 To conclude, the current study showed that specific facets of impulsivity are
277 differentially related to perceived self-regulatory success in dieting and body mass. Moreover,
278 it is the first study showing interactive effects between facets of impulsivity when predicting
279 self-reported success in eating-regulation in children and adolescents and that these interactive
280 effects indirectly relate to higher body mass. Thus, the current study provides information on
281 moderators of the relationship between impulsivity and body mass, that is, under which
282 circumstances impulsivity is associated with higher body mass (when both attentional and
283 motor impulsivity are high). It also provides information on possible mediators of the
284 relationship between impulsivity and body mass, that is, mechanisms of how impulsivity may
285 lead to higher body mass (via low self-regulatory success in dieting).

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416

Table 1

Descriptive statistics of and correlations between study variables

<i>N</i> = 122	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.
1. Body mass index percentile	74.43	32.32	-	-.32*	.08	.11	.01
2. Perceived Self-Regulatory Success in Dieting	12.91	4.11		-	-.23*	-.16	-.20*
3. Attentional impulsivity	10.26	2.71			-	.51*	.11
4. Motor impulsivity	12.23	3.42				-	.05
5. Non-planning impulsivity	10.03	3.33					-

**p* < .05

Table 2

Results from linear regression analyses with impulsivity scores predicting perceived self-regulatory success in dieting and body mass

<i>N</i> = 122	Perceived Self-Regulatory Success in Dieting			Body mass index percentile		
	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>p</i>
Perceived Self-Regulatory Success in Dieting	-	-	-	-2.46	0.75	.001
Attentional impulsivity	-0.25	0.15	<i>ns</i>	-0.38	1.22	<i>ns</i>
Motor impulsivity	-0.06	0.12	<i>ns</i>	0.73	0.95	<i>ns</i>
Non-planning impulsivity	-0.32	0.13	.01	-0.64	1.04	<i>ns</i>
Attentional × motor impulsivity	-0.10	0.04	.02	0.41	0.34	<i>ns</i>
Attentional × non-planning impulsivity	0.01	0.05	<i>ns</i>	-0.64	0.36	<i>ns</i>
Motor × non-planning impulsivity	-0.06	0.04	<i>ns</i>	-0.003	0.28	<i>ns</i>
Attentional × motor × non-planning impulsivity	0.01	0.01	<i>ns</i>	0.02	0.10	<i>ns</i>

Table 3

Conditional direct and indirect effects of attentional impulsivity (independent variable) on body mass (outcome variable) via perceived self-regulatory success in dieting (mediator) at different levels of motor impulsivity (moderator)

Values of the moderator	Direct effects			Indirect effects		
	<i>b</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>p</i>	Effect (bootstrap estimate)	<i>SE</i> (bootstrap estimate)	95% bias-corrected bootstrap CI
Low motor impulsivity (-1 <i>SD</i>)	-1.80	1.67	<i>ns</i>	-0.22	0.58	-1.74, 0.74
Medium motor impulsivity (mean)	-0.38	1.22	<i>ns</i>	0.62	0.46	-0.10, 1.74
High motor impulsivity (+1 <i>SD</i>)	1.03	1.70	<i>ns</i>	1.47	0.71	0.39, 3.32

Figure captions

Figure 1. (A) Conceptual moderated mediation model, in which scores on all three impulsivity subscales, their two-way interactions, and the three-way interaction were used as predictors of both perceived self-regulatory success in dieting (as mediator) and body mass. (B) Empirical moderated mediation model, where only those paths of the conceptual model that reached significance in the current study were retained (also see Table 2). Specifically, an interaction between attentional and motor impulsivity predicted perceived self-regulatory success in dieting ($b = -0.10$, $SE = 0.04$, $p = .02$; Figure 2). Non-planning impulsivity negatively predicted perceived self-regulatory success in dieting ($b = -0.32$, $SE = 0.13$, $p = .01$). Perceived self-regulatory success in dieting, in turn, negatively predicted body mass index ($b = -2.46$, $SE = 0.75$, $p = .001$). There was no direct effect of attentional impulsivity on body mass index, but an indirect effect of attentional impulsivity on body mass index, which was moderated by motor impulsivity: the effect of attentional impulsivity on body mass index was mediated by perceived self-regulatory success in dieting, but only at high motor impulsivity (Table 3).

Figure 2. Simple slopes probing the interaction between attentional and motor impulsivity when predicting perceived self-regulatory success in dieting. Scores on attentional impulsivity negatively predicted perceived self-regulatory success in dieting at high scores on motor impulsivity (+1 SD), but not at low scores on motor impulsivity (-1 SD).

